

Transannular Electronic Interactions of 1,6-Cyclodecanedione Dioxime and its Synthesis

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An interesting ten-membered medium-sized ring compound, 1,6-Cyclodecanedione dioxime is prepared, and its ultraviolet absorption spectra in 95% ethanol and concentrated sulfuric acid are studied. The compound exhibits unusual absorption bands at the wavelengths of 246nm and 286nm, and have the molar absorptivities of 13,200 and 16,800 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ in 95% ethanol and concentrated sulfuric acid respectively. The presence of a strong absorption band in the 246nm region is taken as evidence for this transannular electronic interaction in the excited state. The origin of π - π^* transition (K-band) and its assignment are discussed from the standpoint of the transannular electronic interaction (transannular conjugation)¹. This is an interesting consequence of the stereochemistry of the ten-membered ring.

ONE of the advantages of the molecular orbital theory over early resonance theory is that the former readily accounts for certain electronic interactions between groups which are not conjugated in the classical sense. The purpose of this paper is to describe the synthesis of 1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime, and to discuss the electronic interaction between transannular nonconjugated two $>C=N$ -azomethine chromophore groups in this compound.

Azomethines and oximes show no absorption in the near ultraviolet unless the $>C=N$ -chromophore is involved in any sort of conjugation². In the spectra of conjugated azomethines and oximes the K-band appears in the 220-240 nm region and ϵ max $>10,000^2$. Acidification of the azomethines and oximes, producing a positive charge on the nitrogen, shifts the absorption to the 270-290 nm region².

Experimental

By using Naphthalene I as the starting material, a medium-sized ring compound 1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime IV was prepared. Naphthalene was first reduced to 9,10-Octalin II by lithium metal in *n*-propylamine.³ The peroxide oxidation of the 9,10-Octalin in formic acid followed by hydrolysis produced 9,10-Decalindiol which was further oxidized to 1,6-cyclodecanedione III by lead tetra-acetate⁴. The dione was next converted to 1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime by reacting with hydroxylamine hydrochloride⁵. The sequence of reactions is represented as follows: (Fig. 1).

9,10-octalin II. 51.2g of naphthalene (0.4 mole) were dissolved in 1000 ml of *n*-propylamine in a three-necked flask under nitrogen atmosphere. Then 33.2g (4.8 moles) of lithium were added in small pieces at room temperature with vigorous stirring. After an hr, the solution was decomposed by the cautious addition of solid ammonium chloride till the solution

became colorless. Water was added dropwise to the residues with external cooling. The oily organic layer was extracted with ether and separated from

Fig. 1. Reaction sequence

the aqueous layer. Ether was stripped off and the product was isolated by high vacuum distillation. 42.3g of colorless oil distilling at 60° and 0.1 mm pressure of Hg, were obtained. The yield was 89%.

9,10-Decalindiol. 213 ml of 90% formic acid and 79 ml of 27% hydrogen peroxide were placed in a three-necked flask. 74g of 9,10-octalin were added during a 30 min period under nitrogen atmosphere with stirring at 45° ± 3°. The solution was warmed and stirred six additional hours. The product was diluted to 500 ml with water, and 150g of sodium chloride were added and well mixed, giving oil which soon solidified in the ice chest. The product was collected, washed with water, and dried as a hydroxy formoxy compound. The hydroxy formoxy compound was hydrolysed by adding 80g of sodium

hydroxide in 150 ml of ice-cold water. It was then stirred for one-half at room temperature, and one hour at 75° to 80°. The mixture was diluted with 375 ml of water, a crystalline product was filtered after several hours, washed with water and dried. It was recrystallized from aqueous acetone. The net yield was 80%, or 54g. The melting point was determined to be 89°-90°.

1,6-Cyclodecanedione III. 25g of the molten dihydroxy compound were added to 200 ml of dry benzene. The mixture was treated with 74g of lead tetra-acetate at room temperature during 1½ hr. It was stirred for 2 and ¼hr more and then refluxed for 30 min at 60°. The excess lead tetra-acetate was filtered and washed with 4×17 ml of benzene. The solvent was distilled under a slight vacuum, yielded 1,6-cyclodecanedione which was then recrystallized from petroleum ether. The yield was 87%, or 18g. The melting point was determined to be 99°.

1,6-Cyclodecanedione dioxime IV. Five grams of 1,6-cyclodecanedione was treated with 10 grams of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, 20g of potassium hydroxide, and 80 ml of 95% ethanol. The mixture was heated under reflux for 2 hrs and poured into 500 ml of water. The suspension was stirred and allowed to stand to permit unchanged ketone to separate. The solution filtered, acidified with hydrochloric acid and allowed to stand to permit the oxime to crystallize. The product was recrystallized from ethanol or an ethanol water mixture. The yield was 85%. The melting point of oxime is 231° and is uncorrected. The infrared absorption for hydroxyl group (OH) is at 3695 cm⁻¹. Carbon nitrogen double bond (C = N) is at 1680 cm⁻¹. Ultraviolet absorption spectra are at 246 nm in ethanol and 286 nm in sulfuric acid. Carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen analysis, calculated for C₁₀N₂O₂H₁₈: C, 60.60; H, 9.90; N, 14.14; O, 16.16. Found: C, 60.68; H, 9.12; N, 14.04; O, 16.12.

Discussion

Transannular interaction. The visible and ultraviolet spectra of 1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime have been measured in ethanol, and the compound exhibits an unusual absorption band at 246 nm with a molar absorptivity of 13,200 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (Fig. 2). Similar bands have been observed in the spectra of other ten-membered cyclic systems containing non-conjugated chromophores and have been attributed to transannular electronic interactions^{1,6,7,8}. The weak absorption near 200 nm appears only as a shoulder or an inflection so that its diagnostic value is questionable (Fig. 2).

When the spectra of 1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime was determined in concentrated sulfuric acid a new spectroscopic species appeared which absorbed strongly in the longer wavelength at 286 nm with a molar absorptivity 16,800 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Probably acidification produces positive charge on the nitrogen and shifts the absorption to longer wave-length from 246 nm to 286 nm (Fig. 3). The weak absorption near 215 nm appears only as a shoulder or an inflection (Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. UV Spectrum of 1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime in 95% ethanol.

In the case of 1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime, because of the flexibility and puckering of the ten-membered ring, the nonconjugated two >C = N-azomethine chromophores (oxime groups) can come

Fig. 3. UV Spectrum of 1,6-cyclodecanedione in sulfuric acid.

closer to each other, and assume a *S-cis*-butadiene type conjugation. This permits the orientation of the π -orbitals of both the >C = N-chromophores to be parallel to each other, and thus permit an effective overlap of the π -orbitals (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. π -orbital parallel overlap.

Such an orbital overlap gives rise to bonding and antibonding π -molecular orbitals which encompass both the chromophores. The 246 nm band can then be assigned to the $\pi-\pi^*$ transition (*K*-band). This *K*-band results from $\pi-\pi^*$ transition and are characterized by high absorptivity, $\epsilon_{\text{max}} > 10,000$. The strong *K*-band ($\pi-\pi^*$ transition), $\epsilon_{\text{max}} = 13,200$ probably submerges the weak *R*-band ($n-\pi^*$ transition)².

Hybridization of Nitrogen and Carbon (C_1 and C_6). Carbon-nitrogen double bonds resemble carbon-carbon double bonds in that the two pairs of electrons forming the double bond are in a σ -orbital and a π -orbital. Hence similar electronic transition occurs⁹.

In an oxime $>C=N-OH$, for example, sp^2 hybridization of two $2p$ and the $2s$ atomic orbitals takes place on nitrogen as well as on carbon. sp^2-sp^2 sigma bond is formed between the two atoms, leaving a p atomic orbital on each atom to form a π bond. The nitrogen atom thus uses two sp^2 orbitals to form sigma bonds with the carbon and oxygen atoms, and the third sp^2 orbital holds the nitrogen lone pair. This sp^2 hybridization accounts for the C-N-O bond angle of 120° in oximes.¹⁰ Thus both the atoms C and N of carbon-nitrogen double bonds have trigonal configuration.¹⁰ This condition results in orienting the two azomethine chromophores parallel to each other (Fig. 4).

Degree of transannular interaction. Three medium-sized ring compounds, 1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime IV, 1,6-cyclodecanedione IX and 1,6-dimethylenecyclodecane X, have been synthesized and have been examined for evidence of C=N, C=O and C=C transannular interactions. These compounds IV, IX and X exhibit different degrees of transannular interaction in the same solvent 95% ethanol. 1,6-cyclodecanedione shows $\lambda_m = 287$ nm and $\epsilon_m = 35$; 1,6-dimethylenecyclodecane shows $\lambda_m = 256$ nm and $\epsilon_m = 500$; and 1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime shows $\lambda_m = 246$ nm and $\epsilon_m = 13,200$ (Table 1).

These compounds were chosen first because of the favorable geometry for such interactions of the ten-membered ring with diametrically opposed two similar functional groups and second to check the

weak R-band at 284 nm¹. Similar effects are observed when there can be effective overlap of the

Fig. 5. Transannular interactions $C=N > C=C > C=O$

π -orbitals of the $C=O$ group and the P (or n) orbitals of heteroatom of 1-thiacyclooctane-5-one VI which shows moderately strong absorption near 238 with molar absorptivity^{1,8} 2565 (Fig. 6).

Fig. 6

In order to detect possible transannular interaction between $C=C$ and $C=O$ groups when these groups are located opposite to each other in a ten-membered ring compound, cyclodec-5-en-1-one, VII, an anomalous ultraviolet maximum at 258 nm and molar absorptivity of 472 have been determined⁷. In other ten-membered ring, 1-methyl-1-azacyclodecane-5-one VIII, an anomalous ultraviolet maximum at 221 nm and molar absorptivity of 5610 reflected strong interaction between the $C=O$ group and the nitrogen atom¹⁸ (Fig. 7).

Fig. 7

In other examples, 1,6-cyclodecanedione⁷ IX and 1,6-dimethylenecyclodecane¹¹ X, an anomalous ultraviolet maxima were observed at 287 nm and 246 nm with molar absorptivities 35 and 500 respectively (Fig. 8).

Fig. 8

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF SPECTRAL DATA FOR 1,6-CYCLODECANEDIONE DIOXIME AND RELATED COMPOUNDS.^{1,7,8,11}

Compound	solvent	λ_m , nm	ϵ_m
1,6-cyclodecanedione dioxime	Ethanol	246	13,200
1,6-dimethylenecyclodecane ¹¹	Ethanol	256	500
1,6-cyclodecanedione ⁷	Ethanol	287	35
Cyclodec-5-en-1-one ⁷	Ethanol	258	472
1-methyl-1-azacyclodecane-6-one ¹⁸	Diethyl ether	221	4600
1-thiacyclooctane-5-one ¹⁸	—	238	2535
3-Methylenecyclobutanone ¹	—	214	1500

predicted correlation of the interactions of $C=N > C=C > C=O$ order in the magnitude of the resulting ultraviolet absorption (Fig. 5).

Transannular interactions in other related compounds. There are cases where the $C=O$ and the $C=C$ are nonconjugated in the classical sense but where interaction does occur to produce an absorption band.¹ In structures where this occurs, the $C=O$ and $C=C$ groups must be oriented so that there can be effective overlap of the π -orbitals¹. For example, 3-methylenecyclobutanone V shows a moderately strong band near 214 nm with a normal

The transannular electronic interaction in all these apparently nonconjugated systems is known as transannular conjugation.¹

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